

Economic Miracle Years of Brazil

Volkan Idris Sari (CMU, Heinz College, MPM Program)

Brazil is the fifth largest country both by population and geographic area, and eighth by economic output. O'Neill named Brazil as one of the emerging countries with China, Russia and India. Among its peers, in recent years Brazil has modest growth rates, but higher development progress. Brazil's growth path between 1960 and 1980 was parallel to Asian tigers, while it lagged behind them after 1980. This is the second chance of the country to catch-up developed countries. Results of the first takeoff attempt were exactly opposite the recent figures.

1. Brazilian miracle between 1964 and 1980

Brazil had neither political nor economic stability in early 1960s. Macroeconomic conditions (especially high inflation and large public deficit) and inefficiencies in import substitution industrialization (ISI) process led to GDP stagnation in 1963. There was not a radical policy change after the military coup in 1964, but political and economic stabilization as well as a favorable environment in external markets paved the way for rapid growth.

Although the population of the country increased 2.6 percent annually, Brazil succeeded extremely rapid growth rates between 1964 and 1980. GDP per capita increased 220 percent in total, while it averaged 5 percent in 1960s and 4.9 percent in 1970s. Industry grew 8.5 percent annually in that period, and it was the locomotive of the rapid growth. The rate of investments doubled in ten years period between 1964 and 1974. The share of manufacturing in total output reached 57 percent in 1980 from 18 percent in 1965, while the share of the agriculture was decreasing gradually. Exports as of GDP climbed from 4 percent in 1962 to 9 percent in 1980.

1.a. Rapid industrialization and structural change

Brazil implemented a combination of import substitution and export promotion strategies with a high government intervention. The Brazilian industry tried to build up reputation and learned by doing within the protected domestic markets. Import substitution strategy focused especially on increasing demand for consumer goods that increased as a result of income concentration and more accessible credit markets as well as rapid population growth. By the end of the growth period, the industry was able to produce 2 million cars, 3 million TV and 2 million refrigerators during the selected period.

The foreign trade policy of Brazil both expanded the quantity of industrial exports and diversified exported products. So, the share of exports in the total output increased dramatically. Export incentives, subsidized credit for exporters, high tariffs for imports, tax reduction (even abolishment), and simplified procedures were the main tools to facilitate exports and to protect internal production (Clements and Kim, 1988).

High growth rates changed the structure of the Brazilian economy, and the economic outputs evolved from nondurable agricultural products to more productive and value-added consumer and durable goods. The Brazilian trend was in the same direction with Kuznets cross-sectional analysis. As presented in Figure 1, labor was transferred out of the less productive agricultural

sector into higher productive industry and service sectors. Productivity increased largely not only as a result of structural changes but also uncultivated capacity in early 1960s.

This change became a major source of income growth in Brazil. Consequently, the difference between average incomes in traditional and modern sectors reduced. Rapid population growth and unequal distribution created a huge internal market for consumer goods.

Figure 1. Sector Composition of GDP and Labor

Source: Pinherio et al., 2004

1.b. Increasing savings

The Brazilian miracle confirms investment-driven development models. Investment rates increased gradually from 15 percent in early 1960s to 26 percent in 1975. Brazil benefited from all sources of investments: governmental, private and foreign capital. The establishment of investment banks and government development bank, and cooperation with international development banks created considerable amount of funds for financing huge infrastructure projects and government-owned heavy industries. Macroeconomic stability, modernization of capital markets and introduction of new credit mechanisms led to private saving rates. Beside internal savings, FDI or foreign debts were used for increasing production of durable goods.

Figure 2. Investment Rates (1947-2000)

Source: Ellery et al., 2003

Brazil preferred implementing a squeezed minimum wage policy in order to increase productivity and decrease unemployment. Low level of real wages created higher profits for producers and higher taxes for the state. This surplus also reinvested in production process to expand economic output.

2. The Turning Point: Oil Shock

Oil shocks changed the positive external environment to negative. High raw material prices boomed the bill of the growth. As a growth champion of Latin America during the last decade, Brazil decided to sustain paces of economic growth instead slowing down. This decision was given under the assumption that oil crisis would end soon, and the negative external environment would recover rapidly. Although other developing countries reduced the total output, Brazil expanded ISI and borrowed extremely large amount of debt to finance reasonable rate of growth. Government carried out a huge investment program to relieve the burden of oil shock and to diversify its competitive advantages.

Unsustainable and vulnerable economic environment survived until 1980 because GDP per capita grew on average 3.7 percent, and exports increased by a modest level. Finally, the growth with debt strategy was collapsed and led to macroeconomic crisis (deficit, inflation and devaluation) in 1980.

Table 1. Comparison between Brazil and Asian Tigers

Comparison	Brazil	Asian Tigers
Savings	FDI and foreign capital dependent savings	High internal savings
Industrialization	Combined- ISI and export promotion with high-tariffs	Only export promotion with high-tariffs
Advantages	Low unemployment	International competition, innovation and technological improvement
Income distribution	Highly unequal – dual economy	Relatively equal
Oil shock reaction	Growth with debt	Slow down

Most countries chose ISI policies to have a self-sustaining economy. However, Brazilian case had a different story because of its reliance on foreign capital. Brazil never had higher internal saving rates compared to Asian Tigers. In addition, high population growth rates with inequalities caused a failure in maintaining a dynamic internal market in the long run. Again, educational inequalities reduced the probability of innovation and technological progress. The missing parts of the puzzle were productivity, competition and technological improvement. These are the common disadvantages of ISI policies, and they are not specific to Brazil. However, initial inequalities and low level of human capital in Brazil increased the cost of failure.

3. Poverty and Inequalities

Long term economic growth figures of Brazil do not fit the Kuznets inverted-U curve. The proportion of national income of the top ten percent grew from 39.6 percent in 1960 to 50.9

percent in 1980, and the proportion of bottom half of the population declined from 17.4 percent in 1960 to 12.6 percent in 1980. After 1980, economic surplus collected by national economic growth was spent in development goals such as education and health investments. Then the relation between growth and inequality in Brazil became consistent with Kuznets.

The inequality problem in Brazil is not limited to income inequality. There are also regional disparities between south and north, but the paper focused on income inequality and its reasons.

3.a. Historic background and educational inequality

Brazil was the last Western country abolished the slavery (1888) and always behind the modern world in terms of civil rights, political participation, human capital as well as distribution of wealth. Relatively more eligible conditions in South compared to North America led to existence of scale economies based on slavery. Correspondingly, South America constructed unequal and less democratic institutional structure while homogeneity and broadly accessed institutions were developed in North America. Now, Brazil has the second largest black population after Nigeria, and half of the population is African and mulatto. Not accidentally the majority of poor people is African or mulatto. As a result of this historical context, average salary of a black worker is only 41 percent of a white worker and representation of black people in government always remained at a low level (Engerman and Sokoloff).

Having unequal wealth distribution since slavery period, ruling elite has maintained the privilege of education for their children and refused to pay taxes for public education. Historically, education restricted to the upper and middle classes. For example, during economic boom the government focused on investments in universities instead of increasing school attainment and reducing illiteracy rates. A World Bank analysis on inequality in Brazil proved that a third of overall inequality can be explained by differences in education levels among households (Denslow and Tyler, 1984). Nowadays average number of years of schooling is progressing, but it is still below eight years which is legally required. Accordingly, Brazil has one of the lowest school attainment and literacy rates in Western World. Educational inequality is working as a multiplier effect for income inequality and poverty and creates a vicious cycle of underdevelopment.

3.b. Agribusiness and failure in land reform

Initial income inequality level is very important to the development process, but according to Alesina and Rodrik the equal distribution of land has more importance than any other factor (Alesina and Rodrik, 1994). The development story of Brazil also stresses the importance of the land ownership. Since colonial times, land and agricultural surplus were distributed unequally in Brazil, and various attempts of land reform were failed to change the situation. Besides initial situation, agricultural boom in 1990s and its consequences created more stress on land distribution.

Structural changes in economy led a relative increase in rural wages compared to competitive urban wages and relieved cross-sectoral income inequalities. Nevertheless, government policies raised the inequalities within the agricultural sector. Agricultural output rose sharply with the introduction of rural credit and loan mechanisms, growing local infrastructure investments and increasing productivity. Sectoral changes followed by the emergence of capital intensive agribusiness complexes and accumulation of surplus in a few but large firms (Baer and Filizzola, 2005). To illustrate, establishments larger than 1,000 ha possesses 45% of total rural lands.

Furthermore, agribusiness provided higher wages to its workers than traditional agriculture and strengthened economic power of large landowners.

Unequal land distribution and unsuccessful land reforms triggered the MST movement. Landless people occupied free lands to cease concentrations. Government tried to end occupation by facilitating agrarian reform and redistribution of free and underutilized lands. One can state that inefficiencies in public sector such as long procedures, low transparency and corruption hindered the achievements of land reform. Actually, the resistance of landowners and dualistic structure of society slowed down the process. Land invasions endangered the property rights and diminished investments as well as decreased productivity in agriculture.

3.c. Industrialization strategies and wage policy

Capital intensive modern sector enrichment strategy also worsened the income distribution in Brazil due to three main drawbacks. First, the industry sector could not employ all agricultural workers migrated to cities. Social exclusion and unhealthy living conditions in favelas condemned these people to poverty. Second, the wage gap was widened intentionally in order to relieve labor costs and augment savings by decreasing minimum wages for unskilled workers. During 1960s, the average income increased 32 percent while the minimum wage decreased 25 percent. Third, economic surplus and taxes earned by low wages transferred to skilled labor through high wages and manufacture industry via incentives and subsidies.

The relation between income level and savings draws an S-shape instead of positive linear relationship. So, after a specific level of wealth marginal change in savings is decreasing. Therefore, scholars who interpreted inequalities as a natural result of rapid growth state that future achievement in labor market and education would reverse the effects of capital accumulation. In Brazil, by contrast, the lack of regulation in labor market (for example unemployment insurance and retirement pensions) and concentrated education investments contributed to have one of the most unequal income distribution in history.

On the other hand, unlike South Korea export promotion policies in Brazil tended to favor large firms. Large firms absorbed 90 percent of export subsidies and used more capital intensive techniques than SMEs. So, their equalizing effects remained limited.

3.d. Rapid population growth

One could not neglect the effects of population growth on creating Belinda -a Belgium inside an India- problem (Sachs, 1994). Even during years of economic boom, large population in Brazil created poverty, lower savings and productivity, and economic inefficiencies instead of dynamic labor force, sustainable internal demand and innovation.

Figure 3. GDP per capita and population growth rates

Source: World Bank Databank

Brazil neither sustained its economic growth nor ensured technological and social progress to pass over the Malthusian population trap so that stuck in the second stage of the demographic transition. Between 1960 and 1980, the population of Brazil increased from 72.8 to 121.7 million (67 percent in total and 2.3 percent on average) as a result of historically high fertility rates and declining mortality rates. Figure 3 shows that the economic growth rates were larger than the population growth during economic miracle. In the meantime, headcount ratio was reduced more than a half in those years, but the share of poor people was diminished 34 percent (World Bank, 1995). So, dualistic economic structure limited the expected gains of poor people, and population growth, itself, produced destabilizing effects on development. As the structure of the population changes very slowly, population growth created detrimental effects on society when the economy trends turned from growth to stagnation.

We could explain high fertility rates in Brazil with Gary Becker's household choice model. Poor households tended to have more children because of squeezed minimum wages, unregulated labor market (less access to "missing market") and high child mortality. So, three main outcomes of the vicious cycle of underdevelopment (poverty, population growth and inequality) offsets each other over and over.

Population growth in Brazil had two more negative implications on sustainable development: uncontrolled urbanization and ecological disruption. Rural areas and underdeveloped regions were two sources of migration to cities after rapid industrialization. The share of urban population mounted to 68 percent in 1980 from 45 percent in 1960. The absorption capacity of cities was remained limited owing to unstable economic conditions and urban segregation and exclusion. Poor people could not reach formal labor market as well as housing and social services. That is to say, the emergence of urban infrastructure and new jobs was slower than economic growth and migration. Rapid urbanization caused the formation of favelas which became the source of diseases, pollution and violence.

Industrialization policies of Brazil favored the concentration of economic activities into big cities to benefit from positive externalities of geographic proximity. However, negative externalities of the concentration caused congestion and rapidly expanding pollution in cities. Besides, large agricultural and ranching projects in the environmentally sensitive regions were encouraged by government through incentive and subsidy policies. The extent of Amazon deforestation was the most crucial outcome of the rapid population growth, not just for Brazil but for the entire world. It is estimated that average annual deforestation was 22,228 km² during 1978-1989 period (Baer, 2008).

One can argue that social, economical and ecological cost of Brazilian Miracle exceeded its benefits. It took the advantage of underutilized capacity of the early periods and exhausted all current resources without paying attention to sustainability. The economic debt could only be compensated more than two decades later. On the other, Brazil is still struggling with social debt owed to poor people.

4. Corrective Actions

Human development progress in Brazil was always behind its economic performance. Currently, GDP rank of the country still above its HDI rank. However, recent progress in human development indicators was impressive, and the gap between growth and development is narrowing steadily.

Inequality and poverty figures started to change in Brazil after promoting education attainment since 1980 and increasing investments in health and social policies. Political and macroeconomic stability, raise in minimum wages and local infrastructure projects acted as a multiplier effect and disseminated the outcomes of the social policies throughout whole country. The Real Plan and Bolsa Familia Program led a significant convergence among individual incomes and states. Nowadays, the social assistance programs are more widespread and better targeted to the poor.

Figure 4. Progress in Human Development Indexes (1980-2000)

Source: UNDP

Consequently, the GINI coefficient decreased from 63.3 in 1989 to 54.7 in 2009. Poverty rates dropped dramatically after mid-1990s. In 2009, rates of headcounts living under \$2 and \$1.25 decreased to one third of 1992 figures. Considering indexes in Figure 4, we can conclude that expansion of basic education was the first and most effective tool of the government for ensuring equal income distribution.

5. Conclusion

The relation between inequality and growth is a complex and controversial issue. There was almost a neoclassical consensus on that inequalities during early stages of rapid growth are provisional. However, in recent years there are several studies rejecting neoclassical consensus (Alesina and Rodrik). According to Fisher and Ericson, the direction of the relation depends on individual context of countries and applied policies. My conclusion for the Brazilian case is that Brazil started its growth path with an unequal distribution and implemented disequalizing policies. Right after the miracle years, Gary Fields noted that deliberate unevenness is the central feature of the Brazilian growth. Hence, artificial inequalities could not be solved without government interventions. In other words, Brazil could not ensure sustainable growth and convergence without paying enough attention to inequality problems.

Resources:

- Alesina, A., Rodrik, D., *Distributive Politics and Economic Growth*, 1994.
- Baer, W., Filizzola, M. Growth, *Efficiency and Equity: The Impact of Agribusiness and Land Reform in Brazil*, University of Illinois, 2005, available at http://www.business.illinois.edu/Working_Papers/papers/05-0109.pdf.
- Baer, Werner. *The Brazilian Economy: Growth and Development*, 5th ed. New York: Greenwood, 2001.
- Berg, A.G., Ostry, J.D., *Inequality and Unsustainable Growth: Two Sides of the Same Coin?*, IMF, 2011.
- Clements, B.J., Kim, K. S., *Foreign Trade and Income Distribution: The Case Of Brazil*, Kellogg Institute, 1988.
- Coatsworth, J. H., *Why is Brazil "Underdeveloped" and What Can Be Done About It?*, 6 Harvard Review Of Latin America 7 (2007).
- Denslow, D., Tyler, W. G., *Perspectives on Poverty and Income Inequality in Brazil: An Analysis of the Changes during the 1970s*, World Bank Staff Working Papers Number 601, 1983.
- Ellery, R., et al., *Investment and Capital Accumulation in Brazil from 1970 to 2000: A Neoclassical View*, 2003.
- Engerman, S. L., Sokoloff, K.L., *The Persistence of Poverty In the Americas: The Role of Institutions*.
- Fields, G.S, *Poverty, Inequality and Development*, New York: Cambridge, 1980.
- Fisher, B.P., Erickson J.D., *Growth and Equity: Dismantling the Kaldor-Kuznets-Solow Consensus*.
- Francisco H. Ferreira et al., *Inequality And Economic Development In Brazil*, 2004.
- Latimer, A., Kulkarni, K.G., *Population Explosion and Economic Development: Comparative Analysis of Brazil and Mexico*, available at,

http://www.kulkarnibooks.com/assets/downloads/kishore_papers/paper_with_ashley_latimer_on_population_explosion.pdf.

Person, T., Tabellini, G., *Is inequality harmful for growth?*, *American Economic Review*, 1994, Vol.84.

Pinheiro, A. C., et al., *Brazilian Economic Growth, 1900–2000: Lessons and Policy Implications*, *Global Development Network Conference* (2001), available at http://www.lacea.org/country_studies/brazil.pdf.

Revista, *Harvard Review of Latin America* Volume VI Number 3, Spring 2007.

Sachs, I., *Growth and Poverty: Some Lessons from Brazil*, 1987.

Smith, S. C., *The Meaning of Development: Brazil and Costa Rica*, Case Studies in Economic Development, George Washington University Department of Economics, 2003.

Souza J.A.P., *Institutional Change And Economic Transformation In Brazil, 1945-2004 -From Industrial Catching-Up To Financial Fragility*, United Nations University, 2007.

Williams S., *Why Is Brazil An Emerging Market Economy?*, 2011

World Bank, *Brazil: A Poverty Assessment*, Report No. 14323-BR., 1995.